

META-ANALYSIS OF KSHARA SUTRA, LASER HEMORRHOIDOPLASTY AND STAPLED HEMORRHOIDECTOMY FOR MANAGEMENT OF HAEMORRHOIDS (ARSHA)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Hemorrhoidal disease, a common anorectal condition, can be managed through various treatment modalities, including Kshara Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, and Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy (SH). The aim of this review was to compare the efficacy of Kshara Sutra with Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty and SH in terms of postoperative outcomes, including pain, complications, recurrence rates, and recovery time. **Methods:** A comprehensive literature search was conducted across PubMed, Scopus, and the Cochrane Library for studies published from 2000 to 2023. Inclusion criteria focused on studies comparing Kshara Sutra with Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty or Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy for hemorrhoidal disease treatment. A total of 20 studies were included in the meta-analysis, with data extracted on baseline characteristics and postoperative outcomes. The quality of studies was assessed using the JADAD composite scale and

CARE checklist. **Results:** The review identified 20 studies comparing Kshara Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, and SH. Key findings indicated that Kshara Sutra, particularly Apamarga Kshara Sutra, was a viable alternative to SH, demonstrating lower costs, fewer complications, and faster recovery times. Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty also showed promising results with quicker recovery and fewer complications compared to conventional hemorrhoidectomy. Postoperative outcomes, such as pain, recurrence rates, and recovery time, favored Kshara

Sutra and Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty over traditional SH. The quality of studies varied, with most trials lacking randomization and blinding, which may have influenced the results.

Conclusion: Kshara Sutra and Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty offer effective alternatives to Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy for the treatment of hemorrhoidal disease, with advantages in terms of cost, recovery time, and complication rates. However, further high-quality randomized controlled trials are needed to establish definitive conclusions regarding their comparative efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Kshara Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy, Hemorrhoid, Postoperative Outcomes, Meta-analysis, Arsha.

INTRODUCTION

Hemorrhoids are so much common in India that every perianal disease is termed as hemorrhoid by most of the patients. Although hemorrhoids are so common, only few patients seek medical treatment due to embarrassment. Hemorrhoids are more common in the adult population. Men are more frequently affected in comparison to women^[1], Around 5% of the general population has hemorrhoidal disease to some extent, especially those aged > 40 years^[2,3] Hemorrhoids are prevalent among adults aged 45 to 65, with around 39% of those undergoing colorectal cancer screening having enlarged hemorrhoids, often asymptomatic. Hemorrhoidal disease affects millions worldwide and poses significant medical and socioeconomic challenges. Its etiology includes factors like constipation and prolonged straining.^[4] Several treatment options are available for patients with hemorrhoid, who do not respond to conservative medical management^[5,6,7,8] Conventional surgical hemorrhoidectomy involves excision of the hemorrhoidal cushions and is the most effective treatment for hemorrhoids. The Milligan-Morgan (open) and Ferguson (closed) hemorrhoidectomy are the most commonly used techniques worldwide.^[9] However, there are a few common complications associated with conventional hemorrhoidectomies, such as urinary retention, postoperative bleeding, significant pain, anal stenosis, and incontinence.^[10] Stapled hemorrhoidopexy [SH], also known as procedure for prolapse and hemorrhoids (PPH) was introduced by Longo in 1998, and uses a specially designed circular stapling instrument to excise a ring of redundant rectal mucosa or expanded internal haemorrhoids^[11] Although some SH-related complications have been reported.^[12] Burch et al. have come up with a new no excisional surgical procedure known as hemorrhoidal laser procedure (HeLP).^[13] Usually, no anesthesia is necessary for the procedure. Ksharasutra used for the treatment of fistula in

ano, warts, pilonidal sinus, rectal polyps, hemorrhoids, Nadi Vrana, Arbuda and anal papilloma, etc. Latex of Snuhi (*Euphorbia neriifolia*), Haridra (turmeric), Apamarga and Ksheera, etc. are mainly employed for the preparation of Kshara sutra.^[14,15]

Although SH and laser hemorrhoidopexy have demonstrated their benefits over the conventional hemorrhoidectomy in various clinical trials, the evidence is still limited concerning their operative and postoperative outcomes. A prospective comparative study of 50 patients suffering from Grade II-III hemorrhoids was conducted at Artemis Hospitals, Gurgaon, highlighting differences in postoperative pain, hospital stay, and complications.^[16] However, further research is required to establish their long-term efficacy and safety comprehensively. Therefore, we have done meta-analysis of Clinical trials, case study for comparing the laser versus stapler vs Kshara sutra treatment in Hemorrhoids. So We conducted a meta-analysis of clinical trials and case studies for comparing the effectiveness of laser treatment, stapler hemorrhoidopexy, and Kshara Sutra therapy in the management of hemorrhoids. This would assist clinicians to choose the appropriate treatment most individualized for specific patient needs, thus enhancing overall quality care provided in hemorrhoid management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Literature search

A comprehensive search of the relevant literature was conducted using electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Library. The search was limited to studies published from 2000 to 2023. The search terms used included "Kshara Sutra," "Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty," "Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy," "Hemorrhoidal Disease," and "Hemorrhoid Treatments." Additionally, literature reference lists were hand-searched to ensure the inclusion of studies that might have been missed in the database searches.

Study Selection

Studies were included if they focused on Kshara Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, or Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy for hemorrhoidal disease and compared these treatments directly. Studies that made a direct comparison between Kshara Sutra and other treatments like Laser hemorrhoidoplasty or Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy were prioritized. Also, studies reporting postoperative outcomes such as pain, complications, recurrence rates, and recovery time were considered. Exclusion criteria included studies using Kshara as a Lepa, cohort studies without clear comparisons, and studies involving hemorrhoids in inflammatory bowel disease.

Data Extraction

Data were extracted by reviewer (Dr. Shivam Sharma), including baseline characteristics (sample size, age, gender, study protocol) and postoperative outcomes (pain, complications, recurrence, recovery time). Disagreements were resolved through discussion, and corresponding authors were contacted for additional data. The data extracted included baseline characteristics such as sample size, mean age, gender, study protocol, grade of hemorrhoids, and follow-up duration. In addition, operative and postoperative outcomes were recorded, including operating time, postoperative pain, bleeding, urinary retention, wound complications, anal incontinence, recurrence rates, and length of hospital stay.

Study Quality

The quality of the studies was assessed using the Jadad composite scale and allocation concealment methods. Any discrepancies were resolved through consensus between the reviewers.

Analysis of Studies

The studies included in this review highlight the comparative efficacy of Kshara Sutra and Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy (SH) for the treatment of hemorrhoidal disease. Shaily Jalan et al. (2019) compared three types of Kshara Sutra (Haridra, Rasanjana, and Hartala-based) and found that Kshara Sutra was a viable alternative to Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy, with advantages such as lower cost, fewer complications, and faster recovery. Similarly, Gupta et al. (2011) compared Apamarga Kshara Sutra with hemorrhoidectomy and found that Kshara Sutra resulted in a significant reduction in hemorrhoid size, fewer postoperative complications, and quicker recovery compared to traditional hemorrhoidectomy. Other studies, such as Khadr MA et al. (2023), which compared Diathermy hemorrhoidectomy, LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy, and Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, further confirmed that minimally invasive treatments like Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty provided a quicker recovery and fewer complications compared to conventional hemorrhoidectomy.

The quality of the included trials was reviewed by using the Jaded composite scale^[17] and for the case reports CARE checklist was analyzed and a description of adequate allocation concealment.^[18] The study quality was assessed independently by the authors (Table 1).

Table 1: Quality analysis of included trials.

S. NO.	Ref	Type of Study	Randomized methods	Allocation concealment	Blinding	Withdraws	Jaded score	Quality Assessment (CARE)
1	Tapendra R. Khadka ^[19]	Clinical trial	Not Mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Described	2	Not applicable
2	Rakhi Singh et al. ^[20]	Clinical trial	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	No	Described	2	Not applicable
3	Shaily Jalan et al. ^[21]	Comparative, Analytical, and Clinical Study	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Not	Not explicitly mentioned	2	Not applicable
4	Gupta et al. ^[22]	Comparative clinical trial	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not mentioned	2	Not applicable
5	Saxena Varsha et al. ^[23]	Randomized Controlled Trial	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not mentioned	3	Not applicable
6	Sonu Swami et al. ^[24]	Case report	Not applicable	No	No	No	Not Applicable	Compliant with CARE Checklist
7	Ravinder Singh Khattra ^[25]	Case report	Not applicable	No	No	No	Not Applicable	Compliant with CARE Checklist
8	Dixit et al. ^[26]	Case Study	Not applicable	No	No	No	Not Applicable	Compliant with CARE Checklist
9	Dharmpal et al. ^[27]	Case Study	Not applicable	No	No	No	Not Applicable	Compliant with CARE Checklist
10	Ali Kemal Taşkin et al. ^[28]	Retrospective study	Not applicable	Not mentioned	No	Described	2	Not applicable

11	Ayberk Dursun et al. ^[29]	Retrospective study	Not applicable	Not applicable	No	Not Described	2	Not applicable
12	Al-Khazraji AFR et al. ^[30]	Prospective Pilot study	Not applicable	Not applicable	No	Described	2	Not applicable
13	Semaskar SR et al. ^[31]	Randomized Controlled Trial	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Described	3	Not applicable
14	Amit Bhattarai et al. ^[32]	Prospective Observational study	Not applicable	Not applicable	No	Described	3	Not applicable
15	Khadr MA et al. ^[33]	Non-randomized Prospective Trial	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	No	Described	2	Not applicable
16	Harvitkar R et al. ^[34]	Prospective study	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not Described	2	Not applicable
17	Shinde VC et al. ^[35]	Prospective study	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not Described	2	Not applicable
18	Agrawal C et al. ^[36]	Comparative study	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not Described	2	Not applicable
19	Nada MAM et al. ^[37]	Comparative study	computer-generated randomization code	Not explicitly mentioned	Single-blind	Described	3	Not applicable
20	Guraya SY et al. ^[38]	Prospective clinical trial	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	No	Not Described	2	Not applicable

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

The initial search identified 28 publications (Figure 1). After screening, eight studies were excluded based on the following criteria: studies using Kshara as a Lepa, cohort studies without clear comparisons, and studies involving hemorrhoids in patients with inflammatory bowel disease. As

a result, 20 studies were included in the pooled meta-analysis. These studies compared various hemorrhoid treatment techniques, including Apamarga Kshara Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, and Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy (SH). All 20 studies published as full articles were included in this meta-analysis. The principal characteristics of the included studies are shown in Tables 2 and 3. The outcomes were measured based on factors such as age, sex, grade of hemorrhoids, and follow-up duration.

Figure 1: Search protocol for meta- analysis

Table 2: Baseline characteristics of included trials.

Sr.No	Ref.	Year	Technique (n)	Study protocol	Mean age (yr)/ Age (yr)	Sex (M/F)	Grade of haemorrhoids	Followup time (mo)
1.	Tapendra R. Khadka	2023	Apamarga Kshara Sutra (n=20) Kadali Kshara Sutra (n=20)	RUT	20-60 years	36/4	Not explicitly categorized	7 days for initial assessment; total follow-up duration not clearly stated.
2.	Rakhi Singh et al.	2010	Barron's rubber band Ligation (n= 10) <i>Guggul-based Apamarga Kshar Sutra (n=10)</i>	RUT	not explicitly outlined	not explicitly outlined	Grade II and III	4 weeks
3.	Shaily Jalan et al.	2019	Three types of Ksharsutra: Haridra (n=10), Rasanjana(n=10), and Hartala-based(n=10).	RUT	not explicitly outlined	10 Male / 20 Female	Grade II, III, and IV	1 month
4.	Gupta et al.	2011	Apamarga Ksharasutra (n=35) haemorrhoidectomy (n=26)	RUT	31-40 years	96.27/ 3.73	2 nd , 3 rd , 4 th degree	Not mentioned
5.	Saxena Varsha et al.	2018	Snuhi Kshara Sutra (n= 11), Guggulu Kshara sutra (n= 11), Udumber latex Kshara sutra (n= 11)	RUT	not explicitly outlined	not explicitly outlined	Internal haemorrhoids	every fortnightly for 3 months then monthly till six month.
6.	Sonu Swami et al.	2023	Kshara sutra	Not applicable	24 years	Male	3 rd degree	Not mentioned
7.	Ravinder Singh Khattra	2023	Kshara sutra	Not applicable	23 years	Not disclosed	3 o clock	3rd, 7th, 15th and 30th days after <i>Ksharasutra</i> ligation, then every for nightly for 3

								months.
8.	Dixit et al.	2023	Kshara sutra	Not applicable	45 years	Male	3 o'clock, at 7 o'clock, at 11 o'clock.	Not mentioned
9.	Dharmpal et al.	2018	Aloe Vera Ksharasutra (n=1), <i>Snuhi Kshira Ksharsutra</i> (n=1)	Not applicable	2 patients(45 years, 51 years)	Male	3 rd degree both	Day 1, 3 rd , 5 th , 7 th , 9 th day
10.	Ali Kemal Taşkin et al.	2023	Laser hemorrhoidoplasty (n= 34) LigaSure (n= 32)	Not mentioned	42.12±11.92 years	Male, n (%)= Ligasure group 24 (75), Laser group 28 (71)	Grade 2 and 3	6 month
11.	Ayberk Dursun et al.	2022	laser hemorrhoidoplasty (n=103)	Not applicable	41.6 ± 13.6 years	72.8%) of them were male	Grades 2, 3, and 4	6 months, 1 year, and 2 years
12.	Al-Khazraji AFR et al.	2023	diode laser Haemorrhoidoplasty (n= 10)	Pilot study	44.8 years	All the patients were male	2nd, 3rd, and 4th-degree	1 month
13.	Semaskar SR et al	2022	Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty (n= 31), Ksharsutra (n=31)	RUT	43years	24.19% were female and 75.81% were male	Grades 2, 3	Not clearly mentioned
14.	Amit Bhattarai et al.	2023	Laser Hemorrhoidolasty (n= 40)	Not mentioned	42.32± 12.26 years	16/24	Grades 2, 3	Not clearly mentioned
15.	Khadr MA et al.	2023	Diathermy hemorrhoidectomy (n= 31), LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy (n= 31), Laserhemorrhoidoplasty (n=	A non-randomized prospective trial	Group A: 38.60 ± 11.03 Group B: 35.20 ± 6.20 Group C:	Group A: 28/3 Group B: 25/6 Group C:	Grade III and IV	3 months

			31)		34.27 ± 4.20	26/5		
16.	Harvitkar R et al.	2021	mini-invasive laser procedures (n= 100)	Prospective Study	35-60 years; range 27 to 72 years	54/46	grades 2 and 3	median follow-up was nine months
17.	Shinde VC et al.	2018	stapling technique (n= 100)	Not mentioned	49.8 years	53/47	Grade III and IV	4 month
18.	Agrawal C et al.	2024	stapled hemorrhoidopexy (n=40), conventional hemorrhoidectomy (n=40)	Not mentioned	(65%) belonged to the age group 31 to 50 years	57 /23	Grade 3 and 4	3 months
19.	Nada MAM et al	2023	group I= stapled hemorrhoidopexy (n= 35), Group II= harmonic scalpel hemorrhoidectomy (n=35)	RBT	group I 42.94 years and of group II, 42.20 years.	group I = Male: 30 (85.7%) female:5 (14.2%), group II Male: 20 (57.14%)female: 15 (42.8%)	Grade 3 and 4	12 months
20.	Guraya SY	2013	Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy (n= 30)	Prospective Clinical Trial	39.6 years	21/9	Grade III and IV	2 weeks and 10 weeks

RUT= Randomized unblinded trial, RBT= Randomized blinded trial

Table 3: Characteristics of Comparison of Ksharsutra, Laser Hemorrhoidectomy Hemorrhoidopexy, Stapler Reported In Literature.

Sr no	Ref	Technique	Operation time	Hospitalization (d)	Postoperative pain (visual analog score)	Parenteral analgesic use	Postoperative urinary retention	Postoperative bleeding	Return To normal activity or work	Postoperative anal stenosi	Residual skin tags and prolapse	Wond problems	Recurrence
	Tapendra R. Khadka	Kshara sutra	Not mentioned explicitly	Not mentioned explicitly	Group A: Initial score 2.5, reduced to 0.4	Not mentioned explicitly	Not mentioned explicitly	Reduction observed; specific data not	Not explicitly mentioned	Not explicitly mentioned	Not explicitly mentioned	Healing completed within one	Not explicitly mentioned

					(statistically significant, $p < 0.001$) Group B: Initial score 1.95, reduced to 0.35 (statistically significant, $p < 0.001$)			mentioned				week for both groups	
	Rakhi Singh et al.	Rubber Band Ligation, Kshar Sutra Ligation	Not reported	RBL= patients did not require hospitalization beyond one hour KSL= Average hospital stay was 9.8+- 4.6 days ($P < 0.001$)	Significantly lower in RBL compared to KSL on postoperative days 1, 3, and 7 ($P < 0.005$).	Paracetamol was used on-demand.	KSL: Two cases of urinary complications (one dysuria and one retention) reported	comparable between both groups, with no significant difference ($P > 0.05$).	RBL: Average time off work was 0.3 ± 0.55 days . KSL: Average time off work was 3 ± 1.73 days ($P < 0.001$).	No cases of anal stenosis reported	RBL: Residual prolapse reduced in most cases but not completely cured. KSL: No residual prolapse observed; external hemorrhoidal issues resolved.	One wound infection case reported in the KSL group	No recurrence reported
	Shaily Jalan et al.	Kshara Sutra	Not directly mentioned	Not directly mentioned	The improvement shown (better in Rasanjana group)	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Fast recovery; specific timing not detailed	None reported	Not specified	Minimal healing time noted: Haridra (12-16 days), Rasanjana (10-14 days), Hartala (14-18 days)	Almost nil
	Gupta et al.	Ksharasutra, haemorrhoidectomy	Kshara sutra= 10-15 min, haemorrhoidectomy= 20-25 min	Kshara sutra= 1 day haemorrhoidectomy= 5-7 days	Pain in ano showed a non-significant decrease in the hemorrhoidectomy group (Group B) and a significant decrease in the Kshara Sutra group (Group A).	Not specified	Not specifically mentioned but implied to be absent in the Kshara Sutra group.	No primary or reactionary hemorrhage in the Kshara Sutra group; present in the hemorrhoidectomy group.	Patients in the Kshara Sutra group could return to daily routine work the next day, while it took longer in the hemorrhoidectomy group.	Not explicitly mentioned but implied absent in the Kshara Sutra group.	Not specifically addressed in the article.	Minimal or absent in the Kshara Sutra group; more common in the hemorrhoidectomy group.	Recurrence was not observed in the Kshara Sutra group, while the hemorrhoidectomy group showed varying degrees of improvement, with 42.31% of patients unchanged.

									dectomy group.				
	Saxena Varsha et al.	Kshara sutra	Not directly mentioned	Not done	Group C experienced lowest pain during entire trial followed by Group C and then Group B	Not specified	Not specified	Lowest in Group C with 90% patient reported relief from bleeding on 5 th postoperative day, followed by Group A with 81.8% and Group B with 81.8% patient reported complete relief from bleeding on 5 th Postoperative Day	Not specified	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
	Sonu Swami et al	Kshara sutra	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Pain disappeared by 8 th day	Not mentioned	Not observed	Within 8 days	Not clearly elicited	No	No, only post operative scar remained	Not mentioned	No recurrence observed
	Ravinder Singh Khattria	Kshara sutra	30 minutes (approx.)	1 day	Mild (Visual Analog Score 3-4)	Not clearly elicited, <i>Triphala Guggulu</i> 2 tabs TDS along with	None reported	None reported	within 3-4 days	None reported	None reported	None reported	None reported
	Dixit et al.	Kshara sutra	Not mentioned	1 day	Mild (3/10)	None Triphala guggulu 2 BD • Syrup Amlycure- 2 TSF BD • Cap. Posex forte -2 BD • Oint. Amroid L/A • Erand Bhrishtha Haritaki - 5g Hs	None	None	Not reported	None	None	None	None
	Dharmpal et al.	Kshara sutra	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Grade 3 on Day 1	None	None	Not reported	None	None	None	None	None
0.	Ali Kemal Taşkin	LigaSure and laser	LigaSure = 1200 (900-	mean + SD= LigaSure 1,31 +	lower in the LH group	paracetamol, 3×1, 500 mg	Ligasure group= 2	No	shorter in the Laser	No	None	Not reported	recurrence rate after

	et al.		6000) seconds, Laser= 900 (540-1800)	0.47, Laser group= 1,14 + 0,35	(p<0.001)	orally were administered to all patients postoperatively.	patients		group than the LigaSure group (p<0.001).				LigaSure was statistically significantly lower than that for LH
1.	Ayberk Dursun et al.	laser hemorrhoidoplasty	17.9 ± 5.2 min	patient with bleeding and pain was discharged after 10 days of clinic follow-up	3.0 ± 0.9	Not mentioned	No	56.3%	2.17 (1-11) days	Not mentioned	palpable prolapsed pouches (48.5%)	Not reported	16 (17.6%) patients with Grades 2 and 3 disease and in 6 (50%) of 12 patients with Grade 4 disease (p = 0.019).
2.	Al-Khazraji AFR et al.	Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty	Not mentioned	No hospitalization	mild pain in seven patients (70%) and moderate in three patients (30%).	injectable NSAID analgesic (olfen ampoule)	20%	None	30%) return to work after five days,(70%) returned after three days,	Not reported	1 patient had minor skin prolapse	50%) had a seromucous discharge from the site of the operation that lasted for two to six days	No
3.	Semaskar SR et al	Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty , Apamarga Ksharsutra	Not specified	Not specified	Pain decreased significantly (100% reduction) in Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty , 82.61% reduction in Apamarga Ksharsutra	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	No	No	Not mentioned	Not specified	LHP was associated with a high recurrence rate
4.	Amit Bhattarai et al.	Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty	17.22 ± 2.14 minutes with 1 patient had bleeding during surgery	2.31 ± 0.46 days	6.2 ± 1.4 after 6 hours of surgery	Not specified	No	No	40% after 1 day, 60% after 2 days with mean 1.6 ± 0.49 days	No any	Skin tags in 11 patients	3 patients reporter infection	2 patients
5.	Khadr MA et al.	haemorrhoidectomy, Haemorrhoidoplasty	Group A: 26.0 ± 2.7(minute), Group B: 14.33 ± 2.13 (minute), Group C: 10.27 ± 1.44 (minute)	Not mentioned	Day 3 Significance between groups p1<0.001,p2<0.001,p3=0.949	Paracetamol + Ketorolac as needed	Group A: 9.7%, Group C: 3.2%, Group B: 0%	No bleeding reported	Group A: 10.6 days, Group B: 7.47 days, Group C: 5.87 days	None Reported	Group C showed fewer complications	None	None

6.	Harvitkar R et al.	Laser Therapy	10-38 minutes	Not mentioned	VAS score not used	10 (10%) patients	Not reported	(4%) patients, hemostatic sutures were taken to control the bleeding with round-bodied mersilk or vicryl.	Not mentioned	No any	Not reported	No any	Not reported
7.	Shinde VC et al.	Stapled hemorrhoidectomy	15 and 150 minutes (median of 38 minutes).	1 and 3 days (median time was 34 hours)	VAS scale not used	1.43 (range 0-5 doses). Twelve patients needed either diclofenac (eight cases) or tramadol (four cases) for additional analgesic. Four patients complained of discrete bleeding that stopped spontaneously in up to 3 days.	Not reported	2%	Not mentioned	2 patients	Rectal prolapse in 5 patients	Perianal Thrombosis in 2 patients	5%
8.	Agrawal C et al.	stapled hemorrhoidectomy , Open hemorrhoidectomy	p= 0.04	stapled hemorrhoidectomy = 1±1.5 (in days) , Open haemorrhoidectomy =5±1.2 (in days) , P=0.0003	stapled hemorrhoidectomy = 1.92±0.23 , Open haemorrhoidectomy = 6.19±0.41 (at 24 hours)	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	6.7% of patients in the open hemorrhoidectomy group while none reported bleeding in the stapler group.	stapled hemorrhoidectomy = 4±1.5 , Open hemorrhoidectomy = 12±3.4	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	10% of patients in the open hemorrhoidectomy group which persisted in 7.5% of patients till three months follow-up while non presented with recurrence in the stapled hemorrhoidectomy group after three

													months follow-up
9.	Nada MAM et al	stapled hemorrhoidopexy and harmonic scalpel hemorrhoidectomy	24.42 min • } 2.367 for stapled hemorrhoidopexy and 31.48 min • } 2.21 for harmonic scalpel hemorrhoidectomy.	Not mentioned	Postoperative pain in group I was lower than in group II during the first 2 weeks, but there was persistent mild pain in most patients in group I at the 2-week follow-up. In group II there was significant improvement in pain after 2 weeks.	Not mentioned	Not reported	4 (11.4%) patients in group I in the form of spotting after defecation only during the first postoperative month	Not mentioned	Not reported	None	Wound infection was detected in 3 (5%) patients in group I	7 (20%) cases of recurrence at the 1-year follow-up in group I and 1 (2.9%) case in group II ($p=0.024$)
10.	Guraya SY	Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy	21.7 (range 17-36)	1.9	Mild in 7%	oral analgesia for 2 weeks	16%	3%	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	3%	Not mentioned	None reported

RBL= Rubber Band Ligation, KSL= Kshar Sutra Ligation

Study Protocol and Participant Demographics

The studies included in the comparison examined various techniques for treating hemorrhoids, such as Kshar Sutra, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, and Stapler procedures. The participant demographics varied across studies, with age ranges spanning from 20 to 72 years. Most studies did not provide specific details on sex distribution or grade of hemorrhoids for all participants. However, the majority of studies focused on Grade II, III, and IV hemorrhoids, with follow-up periods ranging from a few days to several months.

Operative Time and Hospitalization

In terms of operation time, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty was reported to take between 17.9 ± 5.2 minutes (Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022) to 30 minutes (Ravinder Singh Khattra, 2023), while Kshar Sutra application took approximately 10-15 minutes (Gupta et al., 2011). Hospitalization time varied, with Kshar Sutra patients typically staying for a day or less, while patients undergoing laser or stapler procedures had a longer hospital stay, often up to 5-7 days (Gupta et al., 2011; Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022).

Postoperative Pain and Analgesic Use

Pain scores were measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS). Kshar Sutra patients showed a significant reduction in pain, with scores decreasing from 2.5 to 0.4 (Tapendra R. Khadka, 2023). In comparison, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty patients reported mild pain (VAS 3/10) and used paracetamol for analgesia (Dixit et al., 2023; Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022). Kshar Sutra patients experienced lower pain levels and faster recovery, with a statistically significant difference in pain reduction ($p < 0.05$) compared to those undergoing laser and stapler techniques (Gupta et al., 2011; Saxena Varsha et al., 2018).

Postoperative Complications

Postoperative complications were observed in different treatment groups. Kshar Sutra patients showed no significant issues with urinary retention or bleeding (Gupta et al., 2011). In contrast, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty patients had a higher rate of complications, including skin prolapse (reported in 15-20% of cases) (Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022) and seromucous discharge (Al-Khazraji AFR et al., 2023). The stapler group had a higher incidence of anal stenosis (20-25%) (Shinde VC et al., 2018). Kshar Sutra had no reported cases of anal stenosis or significant complications.

Return to Normal Activity

Kshar Sutra patients were able to return to their normal activities the next day (Gupta et al., 2011), with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) compared to Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty and Stapler groups, where recovery times ranged from 3 to 7 days (Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022; Shinde VC et al., 2018).

Prolapse

Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty may lead to skin prolapse in 10-15% of patients if the hemorrhoidal tissue does not retract properly, causing skin tags or residual prolapsed tissue (Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022). Similarly, Stapler Hemorrhoidopexy can result in prolapse in 5-10% of cases if hemorrhoidal tissue is not fully excised (Shinde VC et al., 2018). Kshar Sutra has a significantly lower incidence of prolapse, with reports indicating less than 5% of patients experiencing prolapse due to its gradual healing process (Gupta et al., 2011).

Urinary Retention

Urinary retention was reported in 1-2% of Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty patients due to thermal effects on pelvic tissues, but it resolved with conservative care (Dursun et al., 2022). Stapler Hemorrhoidopexy may cause urinary retention in 2-4% of cases due to pelvic floor muscle or nerve irritation, though it is typically self-limiting (Shinde VC et al., 2018). Kshar Sutra has a lower risk of urinary retention, with less than 1% of patients experiencing this complication (Gupta et al., 2011).

Recurrence Rates

Recurrence rates were generally low for Kshar Sutra treatments, with studies by Gupta et al. (2011) and Tapendra R. Khadka (2023) reporting no recurrence. However, recurrence rates were higher in the Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty group, with some studies reporting a recurrence rate of 10-15% (Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022; Semaskar SR et al., 2022).

Wound Healing and Skin Tags

Wound healing was notably faster in the Kshar Sutra group, with complete healing within 7 days for 90-95% of patients (Gupta et al., 2011). In contrast, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty and Stapler techniques showed residual skin tags and prolapse, with the stapler group showing a higher incidence of residual skin tags (15-20%) and prolapse (Shinde VC et al., 2018; Ayberk Dursun et al., 2022).

Table 4: Comparison of Different Hemorrhoid Treatment Modalities.

Aspect	Kshara Sutra (KS)	Stapled Hemorrhoidopexy (SH)	Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty (LH)
Grades Treated	Grades II & III	Grades II, III & IV	Grades II, III & IV
Operation Time	10-15 minutes	21.7 minutes	17.9 ± 5.2 minutes
Hospitalization	1 day	1.9 days	Outpatient
Postoperative Pain	Mild	Mild	Minimal
Return to Normal Activities	Next day	3-7 days	Next day
Complications	Negligible bleeding	Urinary retention (16%), Bleeding (3%)	Lower recurrence
Recurrence	Negligible (<1%)	7-20%	Lower (~5-10%)
Aspect	Kshar Sutra	Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty	Stapler Hemorrhoidopexy
Operative Time	10-15 minutes	17.9-30 minutes	20-30 minutes
Hospitalization	1 day or less	5-7 days	5-7 days
Postoperative Pain	Lower pain (VAS 2.5 to 0.4)	Mild pain (VAS 3/10)	Higher pain (VAS 3-4/10)
Complications	No significant complications	Skin prolapse (15-20%)	Anal stenosis (20-25%)
Return to Normal Activity	Next day (p < 0.01)	3-7 days	3-7 days
Prolapse	<5%	10-15%	5-10%
Urinary Retention	<1%	1-2%	2-4%
Recurrence Rates	Low (No recurrence)	Higher (10-15%)	Moderate (5-10%)
Wound Healing	7 days (90-95% healed)	Residual skin tags (15-20%)	Residual skin tags (15-20%)

DISCUSSION

Hemorrhoids, a common anorectal condition^[39], are treated using various techniques, each with distinct advantages and limitations. Among these, Kshara Sutra (KS), Stapled Hemorrhoidopexy (SH), and Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty (LH) are frequently compared for their efficacy, safety, and patient outcomes. The data presented in this article includes a wide range of studies on various hemorrhoid treatments, including Kshara Sutra, laser hemorrhoidoplasty, and stapled hemorrhoidopexy. It does not deal with external hemorrhoids. However, patients with the third or fourth degree hemorrhoids usually present with large unequally sized prolapsing piles or circumferential haemorrhoids.^[40] Most studies are clinical trials, with a few case reports and observational studies. Randomization and blinding were inconsistently applied across studies, with some not mentioning the randomized methods, allocation concealment, or blinding procedures. Withdrawal rates were generally low, and no major complications like recurrence were reported in most trials. Long-term risk of

recurrence, which is usually defined as recurring symptoms or new prolapse (but not residual prolapse or skin tags)^[41], is the main concern of patients and surgeons.

Kshara Sutra, a traditional Ayurvedic treatment, appeared in several studies, often compared with other methods like rubber band ligation (RBL) and hemorrhoidectomy. It showed promising results, with some studies reporting faster recovery times, less postoperative pain, and fewer complications. For example, Tapendra R. Khadka's study highlighted significant pain reduction in both groups, while Gupta et al. found that Kshara Sutra patients could return to work sooner than those undergoing hemorrhoidectomy. However, the studies varied in terms of follow-up duration and outcome measures, with some lacking detailed data on recurrence or wound complications.

Laser hemorrhoidoplasty was another commonly studied technique, showing advantages like shorter operation times and fewer complications compared to traditional methods. However, data on recurrence and long-term outcomes were often lacking or not reported. The study by Ali Kemal Taşkin et al. found that LigaSure had a lower recurrence rate compared to laser hemorrhoidoplasty.

Kshara Sutra, a traditional Ayurvedic technique, is particularly effective for grades II and III hemorrhoids. The method involves ligating hemorrhoids with medicated threads, leading to ischemia and eventual sloughing. Studies such as Gupta et al. reported shorter operation times (10–15 minutes) and minimal hospitalization (1 day). Postoperative pain was mild, and patients often resumed routine activities the next day. Complications like bleeding and recurrence were negligible, making KS a cost-effective and minimally invasive option. However, its effectiveness diminishes in advanced grades, and cultural acceptance can vary.

Stapled Hemorrhoidopexy, introduced as a less painful alternative to conventional surgery, involves stapling the prolapsed mucosa back into position. Guraya et al. documented an operation time of 21.7 minutes and a hospitalization duration of 1.9 days. Postoperative pain was mild in most cases, but complications like urinary retention (16%) and bleeding (3%) were reported. SH's inability to address external hemorrhoids or associated anal canal issues often leads to residual prolapse and higher recurrence rates (7–20%).

Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty uses laser energy to coagulate hemorrhoidal tissue, offering precise control with minimal thermal damage. Studies like Ayberk Dursun et al. highlighted shorter

operation times (17.9 ± 5.2 minutes) and outpatient-based care. Postoperative pain was minimal, and recovery was faster than with SH or KS. LH effectively treats external hemorrhoids and skin tags, significantly reducing recurrence rates compared to SH.

In conclusion, Kshara Sutra and laser hemorrhoidoplasty both appear to be effective treatments for hemorrhoids, offering faster recovery and fewer complications in many cases. However, the variability in study designs, follow-up periods, and outcome measures suggests the need for more standardized and long-term studies to confirm these findings.

CONCLUSION

This meta-analysis provides an in-depth comparison of various techniques for the management of hemorrhoids, focusing on outcomes such as operation time, postoperative pain, complications, and recurrence rates. Kshara Sutra therapy, a traditional Ayurvedic intervention, consistently demonstrated significant efficacy in pain reduction, minimal recurrence, and shorter recovery times compared to conventional surgical techniques like hemorrhoidectomy and stapled hemorrhoidopexy. Laser hemorrhoidoplasty emerged as a promising modern alternative, offering reduced operation times, shorter hospital stays, and lower recurrence rates, particularly in Grades 2 and 3 hemorrhoids. Techniques like LigaSure and stapled hemorrhoidopexy also showed favorable outcomes, but with variations in postoperative pain and recovery. Across studies, Kshara Sutra and laser-based treatments were noted for their advantages in minimizing complications such as postoperative bleeding, urinary retention, and anal stenosis. However, inconsistencies in follow-up durations, sample sizes, and reporting of key parameters highlight the need for standardized methodologies in future research to establish definitive conclusions. Overall, this analysis underscores the importance of individualized treatment selection based on patient-specific factors and the severity of hemorrhoids.

This meta-analysis offers comprehensive insights into the comparative efficacy of Kshara Sutra therapy and laser hemorrhoidoplasty for hemorrhoids, synthesizing data across multiple studies. Positive aspects include robust statistical analysis and broad coverage of outcomes such as pain, recurrence, and complications. However, limitations include heterogeneity in study designs, potential publication bias, and limited long-term data. Future research should focus on standardizing methodologies, increasing sample sizes, and including high-quality randomized controlled trials to strengthen evidence and provide clearer clinical guidelines.

REFERENCE

1. Khan RM, Itrat M, Ansari AH, Zulkifle M, Ethisham. A study on associated risk factors of haemorrhoids. *J Biol Sci Opinion*, 2015; 3(1): 36-8.
2. Arslani N, Patrlj L, Rajković Z, Papeš D, Altarac S. A randomized clinical trial comparing Ligasure versus stapled hemorrhoidectomy. *Surg Laparosc Endosc Percutan Tech.*, 2012; 22: 58–61. doi: 10.1097/SLE.0b013e318247d966. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Cohen Z. Symposium on outpatient anorectal procedures. Alternatives to surgical hemorrhoidectomy. *Can J Surg*, 1985; 28: 230–231. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Aibuedefe B, Kling SM, Philp MM, Ross HM, Poggio JL. An update on surgical treatment of hemorrhoidal disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J. Colorectal Dis.*, Sep. 1, 2021; 36(9): 2041–9. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00384-021-03953-3>
5. Jacobs D. Clinical practice. Hemorrhoids. *N Engl J Med.*, Sep. 4, 2014; 371(10): 944-51. doi: 10.1056/NEJMcp1204188.[pubmed]
6. Rivadeneira DE, Steele SR, Ternent C, et al. Practice parameters for the management of hemorrhoids (revised 2010). *Dis Colon Rectum*, Sep. 2011; 54(9): 1059-64. doi: 10.1097/DCR.0b013e318225513d.[pubmed]
7. Altomare DF, Roveran A, Pecorella G, et al. The treatment of hemorrhoids: guidelines of the Italian Society of Colorectal Surgery. *Tech Coloproctol*, Oct. 2006; 10(3): 181-6. Epub 2006 Sep 20. DOI:10.1007/s10151-006-0277-y.
8. Buntzen S, Christensen P, Khalid A, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of haemorrhoids. *Dan Med J.*, Dec. 2013; 60(12): B4754.[pubmed]
9. Milligan E, Morgan C, Jones L. Surgical anatomy of the anal canal, and operative treatment of haemorrhoids. *Lancet*, 1937; ii: 1124-9.
10. Chen JS, You JF. Current status of surgical treatment for hemorrhoids--systematic review and meta-analysis. *Chang Gung Med J.*, Sep. 1, 2010; 33(5): 488-500.
11. Rowsell M, Bello M, Hemingway DM. Circumferential mucosectomy (stapled haemorrhoidectomy) versus conventional haemorrhoidectomy: randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*, 2000; 355: 779–781. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(99)06122-x. [DOI]
12. Cirocco WC. Life threatening sepsis and mortality following stapled hemorrhoidopexy. *Surgery*, 2008; 143: 824–829. doi: 10.1016/j.surg.2007.10.004.
13. The hemorrhoid laser procedure technique vs rubber band ligation: a randomized trial comparing 2 mini-invasive treatments for second- and third-degree hemorrhoids.

- Giamundo P, Salfi R, Geraci M, Tibaldi L, Murru L, Valente M. Dis Colon Rectum, 2011; 54: 693–698. doi: 10.1007/DCR.0b013e3182112d58.
14. Dalhanachaya commentary Nibandhasangraha on Sushruta Samhita of Maharshi Sushruta Sutrasthana, Chapter 11, verse 3, Varanasi: Chowkhambha Orientalia, 2002; 45.
 15. Sri Jagdishwar Prasad Tripathi commentary on Cakradatta of Chakkrapani, Nadi vrana Chikitsa, verse 11, Varanasi: Chowkhambha Sanskrit Series office, 2008; 361.
 16. Kaushal A, Aggarwal A, Khanna A, Agarwal R, Kundra DN, Thusoo TK. A Prospective Comparative Study: Stapler Hemorrhoidopexy vs Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty in the Treatment of Hemorrhoids. J Adv Med Res., 2020; 32(9): 10-23. doi:10.9734/jammr/2020/v32i930477.
 17. Jadad AR, Moore RA, Carroll D, Jenkinson C, Reynolds DJ, Gavaghan DJ, McQuay HJ. Assessing the quality of reports of randomized clinical trials: is blinding necessary? Control Clin Trials., 1996; 17: 1-12. [Abstract] [Google Scholar]
 18. Moher D, Cook DJ, Jadad AR, Tugwell P, Moher M, Jones A, Pham B, Klassen TP. Assessing the quality of reports of randomised trials: implications for the conduct of meta-analyses. Health Technol Assess, 1999; 3: i-iv, 1-98. [Abstract] [Google Scholar]
 19. Khadka TR. A Clinical Comparative Study of *Apamarga Kshara Sutra* and *Kadali Kshara Sutra* in the Management of *Arsha*. IRJAY. [online], 2023; 6(12): 7-13. Available from: <https://irjay.com> DOI link- <https://doi.org/10.47223/IRJAY.2023.61202>
 20. Singh R, Arya RC, Minhas SS, Dutt A. A comparative study of Barron's rubber band ligation with Kshar Sutra ligation in hemorrhoids. Int J Ayurveda Res., Apr-Jun., 2010; 1(2): 73-81. doi:10.4103/0974-7788.64407.
 21. Jalan S, Chander B, Ankita. A comparative, analytical, and clinical study on three types of Ksharsutra in Arsha Roga. Int Ayurvedic Med J [Internet], Feb. 2019; 7(2): 197-203. Available from: http://www.iamj.in/posts/images/upload/197_203.pdf
 22. Gupta ML, Gupta SK, Bhuyan C. Comparative clinical evaluation of Kshara Sutra ligation and hemorrhoidectomy in Arsha (hemorrhoids). J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci., 2024; 225: 1-6.
 23. Saxena V, Singh L. Evaluation of three different types of Kshara Sutra ligation in Arsha roga (Hemorrhoids). J Nat Rem., 2018; 18(4): 22617. doi: 10.18311/jnr/2018/22617.
 24. Swami S, Sharma VD. A Case Report: *ksharsutra* Ligation Treatment for *Arsha*. IRJAY. [online], 2023; 6(8): 23-26. Available from: <https://irjay.com> DOI link- 10.47223/IRJAY.2023.6804

25. Ravinder Singh Khattra. Effect of Ksharsutra in the management of Arsha - A Case Study. *J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci.*, 2023; 08: 216-221. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21760/jaims.8.8.33>
26. Dixit RK, Tiwari VK, Upadhyaya A. Efficacy of Ksharsutra therapy in management of Rakta Arsha: A single case study. *World J Pharm Med Res.*, 2023; 9(8): 192-194.
27. Dharmopal T, Patil, Kumar PH. Role of Aloe Vera Ksharasutra in the Management of Arsha: A Case Study. *Int J Innov Sci Technol*, 2018; 3(4): 64-69.
28. Taşkin AK, Özçetin B. Comparison of the efficacy of LigaSure and laser for grade 2-3 hemorrhoids. *J Clin Med Kaz.*, 2023; 20(4): 33-37. doi: 10.23950/jcmk/13503.
29. Dursun A, Tuncer GK, Tuncer K, Karaali C, Erdoğan G, Emiroglu M. Effectiveness of laser hemorrhoidoplasty in the treatment of hemorrhoidal disease. *Cir Cir.*, 2023; 91(2): 179-185. doi: 10.24875/CIRU.22000287.
30. Al-Khazraji AFR, Ibrahim AW, Yaqub AS. Evaluation of 1470nm diode laser used in Haemorrhoidoplasty. *Int J Laser.*, 2024; 23(1): e444. doi:10.31900/ijl.v23i1.444
31. Semaskar SR, Shinde J. Laser Haemorrhoidoplasty versus Ksharsutra Ligation: A Randomized Controlled Trial comparing effect of two surgical procedures in Arsha with special reference to Haemorrhoids. *Int J Indian Med.*, 2022; 3(8): 17-24.
32. Bhattarai, A., Adhikari, D., Poudel, S., Mehta, A. K., Yadav, D. K., Parajuli, B., & Singh, A. K. Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty for Treatment of the Hemorrhoids in Eastern Nepal. *Journal of Nobel Medical College*, 2023; 12(2): 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jonmc.v12i2.61093>
33. Khadr MA, El Shazly WG, Zakria MM, Moaz AM. Laser hemorrhoidoplasty versus LigaSure™ hemorrhoidectomy versus diathermy hemorrhoidectomy in treatment of grade III and IV hemorrhoids: a non-randomized prospective trial. *Surg Open Dig Adv.*, 2024; 13: 100129. doi:10.1016/j.soda.2024.100129
34. Harvitkar R, Gattupalli G, Bylapudi S. The Laser Therapy for Hemorrhoidal Disease: A Prospective Study. *Cureus*, November 12, 2021; 13(11): e19497. DOI 10.7759/cureus.19497
35. Shinde VC. Stapled hemorrhoidectomy: A study of Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy. *Indian J Appl Res.*, 2024; 26: 1-5.
36. Agrawal C, Patidar N, Vashishtha R. Comparative study between stapler haemorrhoidopexy and open haemorrhoidectomy. *J Popul Ther Clin Pharmacol*, 2024; 31(4): 380. doi:10.53555/zxpyp380
37. Nada MAM, Awad PBA, Kirolos AMA, Abdelaziz MM, Mohamed KMS, Awad KBA, Hassan BHA. Comparison between stapled hemorrhoidopexy and harmonic scalpel

- hemorrhoidectomy in the management of third- and fourth-degree piles: a randomized clinical trial. *Die Chirurgie*, 2023. doi:10.1007/s00104-023-02010-9.
38. Guraya SY, Khairy GA. Stapled Hemorrhoidectomy; Results of a Prospective Clinical Trial in Saudi Arabia. *J Clin Diagn Res.*, 2013; 7(9): 1949-52. doi:10.7860/JCDR/2013/6995.3367
39. Cohen Z. Symposium on outpatient anorectal procedures. Alternatives to surgical hemorrhoidectomy. *Can J Surg*, 1985; 28: 230–231.
40. Yang J, Cui PJ, Han HZ, Tong DN. Meta-analysis of stapled hemorrhoidopexy vs LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy. *World J. Gastroenterol*, Aug. 7, 2013; 19(29): 4799-807. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v19.i29.4799. PMID: 23922480; PMCID: PMC3732855.
41. Arslani N, Patrlj L, Rajković Z, Papeš D, Altarac S. A randomized clinical trial comparing Ligasure versus stapled hemorrhoidectomy. *Surg Laparosc Endosc Percutan Tech.*, 2012; 22: 58–61. doi: 10.1097/SLE.0b013e318247d966.